

Terpenoids : Part CXIII. A New Synthesis of α -Curcumene and Dehydro- α -Curcumene

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5-Methyl-1-(*p*-tolyl)-4-hexen-1-ol(V), the key intermediate, was prepared by the Grignard reaction of *p*-tolyl magnesium bromide and the synthon(III). The carbinol(V), was converted into its corresponding bromide (VI) with PBr_3 in dry benzene which upon reaction with lithium dimethyl copper under nitrogen atmosphere at 0° furnished α -curcumene. Oxidation of (V) with Collins reagent provided 5-methyl-1-(*p*-tolyl)-4-hexen-1-one(VII) which was further submitted to Wittig reaction with methylene-triphenylphosphorane to yield dehydro- α -curcumene.

α -CURCUMENE and dehydro- α -curcumene, the monocyclic sesquiterpenes, have been isolated as a major product from the essential oils of Rhizomes of *Curcuma aromatica* Salib by Simonsen and his associates¹ and from the wood of T-oriental² by Japanese workers respectively. Later on, α -curcumene was obtained from a number of other essential oils^{3,4}. On the basis of chemical and spectroscopic studies and their intercorrelations, formulations I and II have been assigned for α -curcumene⁵ and dehydro- α -curcumene².

Starting with different materials and through different procedures, various groups of workers have reported the syntheses of α -curcumene⁶⁻⁹ and dehydro- α -curcumene^{10,11}. In this communication, we wish to report a new approach towards the synthesis of said compounds by making use of a synthon, 5-methyl-4-hexen-1-ol (IV)¹². The sequence of reactions employed is shown as under :

5-Methyl-4-hexen-1-ol (IV) was submitted to Grignard reaction with *p*-toluene magnesium bromide(III) to give, the key intermediate, 5-methyl-1-(*p*-tolyl)-

4-hexen-1-ol(V) in 78% yield. The carbinol (V), on treatment with phosphorus tribromide in dry benzene, was converted into its corresponding bromide (VI). The compound (VI) was subjected to the reaction of lithium dimethyl copper¹³, under nitrogen atmosphere, at 0° when 2, 6-dimethyl-1-(*p*-tolyl)-hexane-2(I) was obtained which was further purified by column chromatography over neutral alumina using pet. ether as an eluent followed by vacuum distillation to give (I) in 65.8% yield. The pure synthetic sample showed a single spot on tlc. IR spectrum of the synthesised hydrocarbon (I) had comparable bands with those reported for naturally occurring α -curcumene⁸.

Oxidation of the carbinol (V) with excess of Collins reagent¹⁴ afforded 5-methyl-1-(*p*-tolyl)-4-hexen-1-one (VII) which was characterised by its 2, 4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone derivative (red needles from ethanol, m. p. $242^\circ-242.5^\circ$). The ketone (VII) was finally submitted to Wittig reaction¹⁵ with methylenetriphenylphosphorane to provide dehydro- α -curcumene which was purified by chromatography over neutral alumina and elution with pet. ether ($40^\circ-60^\circ$). TLC showed a single spot (Rf. 0.83, pet. ether, $40^\circ-60^\circ$). IR spectra of the synthesised hydrocarbon (II) had compatible bands with those reported for naturally occurring dehydro- α -curcumene².

Experimental

Boiling points are uncorrected. IR spectrum were taken on Perkin-Elmer 337 using sodium chloride optics (thin film).

5-Methyl-1-(*p*-tolyl)-4-hexen-1-ol(V) : Grignard reagent was prepared from magnesium (3.2 g) and *p*-toluene bromide (23.0g) in dry ether (100 ml). This was then cooled in ice-cold water and the aldehyde (III, 10.0g) in anhydrous ether (30 ml) was added dropwise with stirring and left overnight. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 1 hour and then decomposed with ice-cold saturated ammonium chloride solution. The hydrolysate was stirred for 1 hour in cold and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was dried, solvent expelled and distilled under vacuum to afford

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(IV, 14.2g) in 78% yield, b. p. 145°-50°/5mm. η_D^{25} 1.5225; ν_{max} 3300-3400 (-OH), 1600, 815 (triply substituted double bond), 1380, 1125 and 825 cm^{-1} (1 : 4 disubstituted benzenes). (Found : C, 82.17; H, 9.95. $C_{14}H_{22}O$ requires C, 82.35; H, 9.80%).

5 Methyl-1-(p-tolyl)-4-hexenyl bromide (VI) : A mixture of the carbinol (IV, 5.0g), thiophene free dry benzene (100 ml) and four drops of pyridine was chilled in a ice-salt bath. To this was added phosphorus tribromide (3.3g) dropwise during 30 minutes and left overnight. Finally it was warmed at 60° for 2 hr. Thereafter the contents were cooled and poured slowly with stirring into ice-water and extracted with ether. The ether-benzene extract was washed with 5% sodium bicarbonate solution, dried (Na_2SO_4) and solvent expelled. There was no infrared absorption in the hydroxy region.

α -Curcumene I : To an ice-cold slurry of cuprous iodide (13.3g) in anhydrous ether (200 ml) under nitrogen atmosphere was added with stirring by injection from a dry syringe, ethereal methyl lithium (1.59 M, 87.7 ml). The resulting solution containing lithium dimethyl copper reagent was stirred for ten minutes at 0° and to it then a solution of bromide (VI, 4.0g) in ether (20 ml) was added dropwise. The reaction mixture was stirred for another 4 hr. at 0° and left overnight at room temperature. The contents were cooled, decomposed with 20% sodium potassium tartarate and extracted with ether. After washing with water, drying and evaporating the solvent, the residue upon distillation under vacuum afforded the compound (II, 2.0 g) in 65.8%, b. p. 107°-110°/6 mm η_D^{25} 1.5055. TLC showed a single spot (solvent system : Pet. ether : benzene : 4 : 1). ν_{max} 1660, 815 (triply-substituted double bond), 1385, 1190, 1120, 1075 and 825 cm^{-1} (1 : 4 disubstituted benzene). (Found : C, 89.03; H, 10.97. $C_{15}H_{22}$ requires C, 89.14; H, 10.86%).

5-Methyl-1-(p-tolyl)-4-hexen-1-one (VII) : Chromium trioxide (12.0 g) was added in small amounts to a well cooled solution of anhydrous pyridine (18.8 ml) and methylene chloride (100 ml) with stirring. The contents were further stirred for 15 minutes at room temperature. To this, now added the carbinol (V, 4.0g) in one lot. A tarry black deposit separated out immediately. After stirring it for additional 25 min, the solution was decanted and the residue was extracted thrice with methylene chloride. The combined organic phase was washed with brine solution and dried ($CaCl_2$). Solvent was expelled and the residue upon distillation under reduced pressure gave 3.6g of the pure ketone in 74% yield, b. p. 107-8°/3mm η_D^{27} 1.4953. This ketone gave a single spot on TLC (solvent system : benzene : n-hexane : 1 : 1). ν_{max} 1695 (carbonyl), 1380, 1120, 812 and 720 cm^{-1} (1 : 4 disubstituted benzenes).

The above ketone formed a red dinitrophenyl hydrazone derivative which was recrystallised from ethanol m. p. 242°-242.5° (Found : N, 14.43. $C_{20}H_{22}N_4O_4$ requires N, 14.65%).

Dehydro- α -curcumene (II) : To the methylene triphenylphosphorane, prepared from sodium hydride (0.12 g) in DMSO (3 ml) and methyltriphenylphosphonium iodide (2.0g) in DMSO (5 ml) under nitrogen, was added the ketone (VII, 1.0g) in dry THF (5 ml), and stirred for one hour and left overnight. The contents were heated at 50° for 1 hr. The usual work up of the reaction mixture gave a residual oil which was chromatographed over alumina using pet. ether (40°-60°) as eluent. The hydrocarbon fraction was finally distilled under reduced pressure to afford dehydro- α -curcumene. (II, 0.6g) in 60% yield, b. p. 110°-15°/4 mm η_D^{27} 1.4914. TLC showed a single spot (solvent : n-hexane). ν_{max} 3050, 1600, 890 ($\text{>C}=\text{CH}_2$), 1520, 1480, 1125, 815 (1 : 4-disubstituted benzenes), 1630 and 825 cm^{-1} (triplysubstituted double bond). (Found : C, 89.62; H, 10.38. $C_{15}H_{20}$ requires C, 89.94; H, 10.06%).

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